

Possible Relation Between Quantum Mechanical Cycling $\exp(iEt)$ and the Correspondence Principle and Physical Oscillating Objects Like Phonons and Photons

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A value of the average momentum at a point in space may not give information about the times at which each momentum used in the calculation occurred at the point. For example, one could calculate the average at a specific time t or each momentum p_i might be associated with a different time t_i . For a quantum mechanical particle in a potential, the potential may stir up different plane waves at different times in a cycling motion dictated by $\exp(iEt)$. The higher E , the faster the frequency and the smaller the time interval during which cycling occurs. This cycling involves the quantum system shifting from one momentum to another to create an average momentum at each point in space. If this time is small, then one may imagine an average kinetic energy at a point x at t_1 (with a very small time error) and a different average kinetic energy at t_2 (also with a very small time error). This averaging process would then resemble a moving classical particle, in addition to following classical probability flow similar to fluid flow. In addition, the cycling of the momentum appears to be a physical phenomenon and seems to indicate a kind periodic interaction with the potential which may be associated with periodic objects such as phonons and photons.

Quantum Mechanics and Averaging

It is possible to write the Schrodinger equation as:

Sum on $p \quad p^2/2m \sin(px)/W(x) + V(x) + E \quad ((1))$ with $W(x)$ being the wavefunction

Here, the first term represents the average kinetic energy at a point x , which combines with the classical mechanical $V(x)$ at x to give a constant energy at each point x . It was argued in (1), that one could imagine that a quantum particle placed in a potential would stir up many plane waves through interactions with the potential. The plane waves, themselves, were argued to be representations of zitterbewegung motion of particles (2). Thus, these plane waves indicate that a particle may be at different points in space with certain probabilities within say a wavelength. There may be an underlying deterministic motion to this zitterbewegung, but quantum mechanics treats them in a statistical manner. It should be argued that time is also involved as the particles undergoing zitterbewegung can be in different positions at different times. In addition, the plane waves stirred up by the potential may be created at different times. Thus, the average in ((1)) may be picking different momentum terms at very different times. It was argued (2), however, that quantum mechanics of bound states is driven by physical cycling $\exp(iEt)$, thus the different momentum states should be created within a time interval of $1/E$. If E becomes large as it does for high energy eigenvalues, then this cycling time becomes small. In such a case, one can consider the average kinetic energy in ((1)) at a position x as being taken during a small time interval of the order of $1/E$. Since there is an average kinetic energy at x , one

would expect that something is moving to x_1 at t_1 . Given x_1 , there will be a new average kinetic energy which can be calculated in a time interval of $1/E$. Thus, the quantum averaging process of ((1)) for high energy eigenvalues begins to mimic the motion of a deterministic classical particle. This may help to explain why high energy eigenvalue quantum mechanical solutions are said to approach classical mechanical ones.

For the ground state quantum mechanical solution, the energy is low and $1/E$, the cycling time is large. For an oscillator, the ground state energy is $\hbar(\omega/2)$. Thus, the time needed to calculate the average kinetic energy at a point x in ((1)) $1/E$ is of the order of the period of the mechanical frequency of the oscillator. Thus, this ground state does not seem to mimic a classical particle as one requires almost the entire cycle time in order to calculate average kinetic energy values even at one point. This is a purely quantum mechanical statistical state. Nevertheless, the cycling mechanism is the same as that for a high energy eigenvalue, just the period is much longer.

For an oscillator, it can be shown that high energy Hermite polynomial wavefunction values begin to approach the classical density $dt = dx/v(x)$ with $\frac{1}{2}m v^2 = E - \frac{1}{2}kx^2$. (3) In (3), dt is used as a measure to determine how much time a particle spends in a region dx and this is called the spatial probability density. One might try to obtain this result using probability flow. Imagine that one has a small box with probability density d_1 at x_1 with velocity v_1 . At x_2 one has density d_2 with velocity v_2 . To have continuity one may set $d_1 v_1 = d_2 v_2$. A solution is $d_1 = 1/v_1$. If such an argument is valid then quantum mechanics, at high energy values, mimics probability flow equations. The result is only valid at high energy eigenvalues, because it is only at such high values that one can calculate an average density in a small enough time that one can say that one has a density d_1 at x_1 at t_1 . For lower energy eigenvalues, the time is spread out too much to have this localization.

Note: In (4), the author argues that quantum mechanics can be derived from the probability continuity equation $d/dt \text{ density} + \text{grad density} * \text{momentum} = 0$.

Cycling and Periodic Objects Such as Phonons and Photons

It is argued that the cycling of momentum values in ((1)) $\exp(iEt)$ is physical. This means that there may be something regulating or driving this cyclical motion. For the case of a quantum oscillator, one speaks of phonons as being excitations which are associated with the energy eigenvalues $E = \hbar(n + \frac{1}{2})\omega$. For the ground state, $n=0$, one may argue that there is still a kind of cycling motion related to the mechanical frequency ω , even though the overall energy is $\frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega$. A phonon has energy $\hbar \omega$, so it may be hard to argue that there is a phonon in the ground state, but there is a cyclical motion $\exp(iEt)$ with E being the ground state energy, just as there is in excited states. One may argue that there is some kind of periodic object present even in the ground state, but that it cannot be released as it can in higher states, i.e. by the emission of a phonon. It is this physical periodic object which may regulate the frequency of cycling and hence the time required to calculate averages, such as average kinetic energy. Given that a

quantum system is a cycling one ($\exp(iEt)$), one may argue that it is not surprising that physical periodic objects such as phonons and photons can excite or be emitted by such quantum systems. For example, phonons have been seen to excite artificial atoms. It is argued that these actually interact in a periodic way with the potential which is cyclically producing different plane wave states.

In (2), it was argued that one could model fermion solutions of the Einstein energy-momentum equation $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$, with m being the rest mass, by 2x2 matrix particles which exhibit zitterbewegung. These particles exhibit a frequency $\exp(iEt)$. These particles, in turn, could be placed in a potential which would stir up different "plane waves", with plane waves modeling the zitterbewegung of these particles. In this note, we wish to go a step further and speculate that there may actually be a resonance established for each quantum energy state represented by $\exp(iEt)$. A 2x2 matrix particle may be considered to be a physical resonance, but when placed in a potential, a new resonance is established. One might try to argue that these resonances are like periodic objects such as phonons or photons. This might explain why quantum states readily interact with such periodic objects.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue that averaging can occur over long periods of time and that it is only for high energy eigenvalues that the averaging occurs in a short period of time. If that is the case, then for high energy eigenvalues, quantum mechanics approaches fluid flow and also mimics classical mechanics. We have further argued that the averaging is related to the physical cycling which occurs in quantum mechanics $\exp(iEt)$. We have speculated that this cycling may be associated with a physical periodic resonance similar to photon or phonon.

References

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